

SMALL BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT DIRECTIONS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Annotation. *The article analyzes the development of the digital economy, the growth of the expected efficiency of small business in the private sector of the country, as well as the development of small business.*

Keywords: *digital economy, transactions, small business, trade, innovation, blockchain, business, innovation.*

АННОТАЦИЯ. *В статье анализируется развитие цифровой экономики, рост ожидаемой эффективности малого бизнеса в частном секторе страны, а также развитие малого бизнеса.*

Ключевые слова: *цифровая экономика, транзакции, малый бизнес, торговля, инновации, блокчейн, бизнес, инновации.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada raqamli iqtisodiyotning rivojlanishi, mamlakatimizning xususiy sektorida kichik biznesning kutilayotgan samaradorligining o'sishi, shuningdek, kichik biznesning rivojlanishi tahlil qilinadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *raqamli iqtisodiyot, tranzaktsiyalar, kichik biznes, savdo, innovatsiyalar, blokcheyn, biznes, innovatsiyalar.*

As countries with open economies develop against the backdrop of globalization, digital technologies are directly contributing to the growth of society. Modern technologies and platforms have helped businesses and individuals reduce costs by minimizing personal contact with customers, partners, and government agencies, as well as making interactions faster and easier. As a result, a network-based, digital or electronic economy has emerged.

The main source of the digital segment of the economy is the growth of the transaction sector. In developed countries, this figure is more than 70% of GDP, combining public administration, consulting and information services, finance, wholesale and retail trade, as well as services (communal, private and social).

The rapid development of digital technologies in the country's economy will directly stimulate the emergence of new financial processes in small business and private entrepreneurship. This is a clear example of the expansion of markets

through the creation of new segments of telecommunications, the introduction of new mobile and web developments.

Now, old and new companies that use IT tools to create new services and business models around the world are creating strong competition for companies that are leaders in many areas.

According to forecasts, in the coming years, the macroeconomy is expected to be strongly dependent on producers based on lean production, additive, nano and biotechnology criteria. In this regard, the amount of information required for good governance will increase, and the structure of production and citizen dialogue, business and government will undergo significant changes.

Digital technology is dramatically changing more than 50 percent of the economy. This view is based on the fact that information technology and digital platforms are drastically changing business models, eliminating intermediaries for their effectiveness and optimizing processes. [1]

The World Bank estimates that a 10 percent increase in high-speed Internet users could increase annual GDP from 0.4 percent to 1.4 percent.[2]

The growth of the digital economy's share of the country's GDP by about 20 percent annually (around 7 percent in developed countries) is also seen as an indicator of its importance.

In 2010, the Boston Consulting Group estimated the scale of digitization at \$ 2.3 trillion (4.1 percent of GDP) for a group of 20 countries. If this trend continues, in 10-15 years the share of such an economy in world GDP will approach 30-40%.

In developing economies, the IT sector employs about 1 percent of the population, creating relatively few jobs compared to others. However, the rise of IT will lead to job creation in other areas where new technologies are being developed (for every 1 new job created in IT, there are 4.9 jobs in related industries).[2]

The digital economy is boldly opening up new horizons for entrepreneurs and self-employed people.

Often, the contribution to the development of the IT sector leads to the development of the economy, the creation of new jobs, the emergence of new types of services for people and businesses, the reduction of costs in e-government projects.

At the same time, the overall effect of the application of information technology is less effective than expected and is not evenly distributed.

To get the most out of such investments, a better understanding of the interaction of technology with other factors called “analog fillers” is required in a report prepared by the World Bank.

Uzbekistan is also taking important steps to strengthen the regulatory framework for the digital economy. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 3, 2018 No PP-3832 “On measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan” the body was appointed, the issues of crypto-asset turnover and its regulation were clarified.[3]

Introduction and development of activities in the field of crypto-assets turnover in the Blockchain Technology Development Program for 2018-2020, including through the creation of a legal framework for the organization of these activities, including the possibility of selling crypto-assets on local and international crypto-exchanges; From January 1, 2021, the introduction of “blockchain” technology in the activities of government agencies, including in cooperation with other government agencies and organizations, public procurement, public services, verification of personal data, to the system of corporate governance of large commercial organizations in which the state participation in the charter capital is a priority, including the improvement of business processes, optimization of production, administrative and operational processes, as well as the introduction of modern management and resource management provided.

PP-3926 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 2, 2018 “On measures to organize the activities of crypto-exchanges in the Republic of Uzbekistan” and “Digital Trust” dated September 2, 2018 Resolution PQ-3927 “On the establishment of a support fund” also plays an important role in the development of the digital economy.

The development of digital innovations in small businesses to ensure the economic security of the country can make a sharp turn in the development of food, energy, environmental, financial security of the country in all respects. In other words, the introduction of digital innovation management system (SaaS model) in favor of small businesses in a single country can achieve positive results not only in the domestic food chain but also in foreign trade. [4]

Small business and new business processes have a special place in the mechanism of sustainable economic development of our country. Because small business not only develops innovative potential, but also creates decentralized jobs as additional income from the budget. According to German Gref, Director of Sberbank, today is a time when societies are already moving from the information

stage to the digital stage on a large scale. He also said, “Digitalization is a new wave that will increase the share of small business in GDP. He asserted radical modernization will happen to all existing enterprises, but most importantly, digitalization opens up great opportunities, and there are many new opportunities to start and succeed in your business. [5]

The interaction of the participants of the economic process based on the active use of information technology in the digital economy is important for 3 stages:

- markets and sectors of the economy;
- platforms and technologies;
- Development of platforms and technologies and conditions for effective interaction, development of market participants and sectors of the economy (areas of activity) and legal regulation, information infrastructure, human resources and information security. [6]

Among the obvious advantages of digitizing the economic system are:

- Increase labor productivity through robotization and at the same time reduce production costs;
- Businesses that follow the trends of the economic system will have an undeniable competitive advantage over other companies.
- market participants acting in the traditional format;
- creating new jobs;
- Ability to reduce poverty and social disparities. [7]

At the same time, the impact of the digital economy can not only open up new opportunities, but also create new market barriers. Small businesses, in particular, are the most sensitive to changes in the external environment.

Today, small business is one of the weakest players in the economic sector. Therefore, positive work is being done through government support and the development of the digital economy.

Taking into account the small business structure and the key transformational elements of the digital economy, it is possible to create growing reserves and maximize profits in the network. In this context, the main trends in changing the economic system that have the greatest impact on small business are:

- a) Active development of the services market, including outsourcing boundaries under the influence of “elimination” of production.
- b) Robotics
- c) Changing the channels of interaction of the business-state
- d) Rapid growth of the Uber model, etc. [8]

In general, the development of the digital economy will not only increase the literacy of the population, but also allow the expansion of new innovative businesses.

Development of the digital economy of Uzbekistan - competitiveness and national development, production of high-tech products and the use of digital technologies for the welfare of the population. 'strengthening, motivating, shaping needs and wants.

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